

Modelling social dynamics in communities using HUMAT

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1: Introduction

Communities are the natural social structure of humans, often organised around a set of shared resources. In ancient history, human tribes could be found in places with a good natural variety in food and safety. Today many of us live in urban neighborhoods, providing a home, supermarkets, schools and hopefully meaningful work not too far away. Neighborhoods are experiencing different dynamics that affect the satisfaction of the people. For example, the increase in car-ownership had an enormous impact on the use of public space, safety and environmental quality (sound & air). Sometimes a neighborhood is changing because of an aging population, also resulting in changing needs.

In the policy process often trade-offs have to be made between community interests and the interest of the larger municipality. Policy is increasingly becoming community oriented (Jager, Yamu, 2019). Whereas in the past municipalities often decided what was best for a neighborhood, nowadays co-creation is an increasingly popular model for collaboration. This communication between top-down policy and bottom-up community dynamics is an important driver for effective collaboration. When “deciding for” successfully changes in “deciding with”, the resulting outcomes are often more satisfactory for all people involved.

The scale and complicatedness of plans may have an impact on the complexity of the social dynamics, and hence on the collaboration process itself. The more different outcomes are associated with a plan, and the larger the differences between people concerning their expected benefits versus losses, the more likely it is that networks of interest groups emerge, and conflicts have to be resolved. The question is how a municipality, carrying the formal responsibility for the implementation of plans, can identify the risk of conflicts and mitigate these in an early stage by structuring the communication process. For example, how does a community composition affect the resulting social dynamics? Do different networks with different interests exist, and how do they interact. Can this interaction be supported by e.g. temporal project groups or fixed neighborhood councils? To explore this in a systematic way, a social simulation tool can be developed to model different cases.

2: Demands for a community simulation tool

The computer simulation of humans in a community requires an architecture that is capable of combining perception, motivations, decision-making and communication, and hence requires an integrated architecture. Such an integrated architecture combines and causally connects different theoretical notions on the different elements of relevance, and thus can be considered to be a computational social theory (e.g., Vallacher, Read & Nowak, 2017). Several architectures aimed at integrating different theories are available, e.g. the InnoMind simulation model (Schröder & Wolf, 2017), Polias, developed by Brousmiche et al. (2016), the FEARLUS framework (Polhill et al. 2001; Gotts & Polhill 2009) and the Consumat approach (Jager et al. 2000). Issues that seem to be relevant in modelling social dynamics in communities relate to (1) the formation of networks and interest groups in the development of plans, and (2) the processes that drive agents to convince specific other agents of their opinions.

Concerning the challenge of representing networks on or simulation models we have to start with the identification of how people organise themselves in community groups to improve their environment. An important social dynamic in community processes is the formation of different networks of people sharing interests. Within social simulation models the principle of “similarity attracts” is a well known principle (e.g. Jager, 2017). Data have to be collected and implemented in the modelling framework on how groups sharing particular interest grow, and groups having conflicting interests interact. These network dynamics have to be captured in order to develop an understanding of the underlying social complex dynamics. For example, a plan to reduce car traffic in a neighborhood may be supported by people living in the neighborhood for safety and environmental quality reasons, but shopkeepers may fear a decline in of their business. People emphasising safety may discuss this with parents on a schoolyard, an environmental working group may be formed discussing air and noise pollution, and shopkeepers may voice their concerns through the media. In most social simulation model a fixed network is being used, and small-world or scale free architectures are often used to grow such networks. However, in understanding the social dynamics surrounding local planning issues we need to be capable of letting networks grow on the basis of shared interests. Ideally empirical data reveal what dimensions of similarity play a role in this formation of networks, and what the resulting properties of different networks are. Parents in schoolyards may display a spatially condensed clustered network, whereas a network of shopkeepers may be more starlike if a strong opinion leader (or formal representative) is present. This network formation is a first challenge we need to address.

A second challenge is modelling the communication between actors. Many social simulation models have been developed addressing the conditions under which agents collect social information to make decisions. However, in the community dynamics we are studying we encounter people that are very motivated to convince others of their opinion. Sometimes conflicts develop and people avoid further contact (rewiring network). When plans are made to

change the neighborhood, discussions may arise. Especially when many people are expecting their situation will change, differences in these experienced changes and underlying values may play a key role in the motivation of actors to engage in discussions.

A psychologically plausible architecture addressing when an agent has the urge to communicate, and specifically with whom, is not available yet. We acknowledge that outgoing communication often serves to let other people change their opinions and behaviour, which is aimed at improving the outcomes for the sender. And these outcomes may relate to (expected) experiential outcomes, the social connectedness and the (core) values a person has. Hence we propose that the motivation of a simulated agent to communicate to another agent is based on an experienced dissonance between experienced outcomes and expected outcomes if another person changes its opinions/behaviour.

Integrating these ideas on communicative networks and motivations to convince others has led us to developing an agent architecture that can be used to simulate community social dynamics in communities.

3: The HUMAT as an integrated model

The HUMAT architecture has been developed as a basic architecture for constructing artificial populations where the agent cognitions, decision-making and social interactions are based on social scientific theory. Real world social dynamics, such as social innovations, opinion dynamics and behavioural transitions (e.g., Nyborg et al, 2017) involve the behaviour and communication of many different people connected in social networks, who make decisions on their behaviours on the basis of their interests, share information with others, and are susceptible to norms. They are repeatedly confronted with difficult choices, as trade-offs often have to be made between short term gratification, social impacts of their choices and their personal values. Interaction between people may result in dynamics such as diffusion of new behaviours, opposite opinions, and tipping points in the dominance of particular norms.

The HUMAT architecture formalises a number of drivers and processes underlying social dynamics. In the HUMAT architecture, the process of taking action can be divided into several stages depicted in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Taking action in HUMAT.

3.1: Evaluate behavioural alternatives

The initiation of agent activity starts with the different **needs** being satisfied (or not) by different behavioural alternatives. Several theories on needs exist, offering different but overlapping taxonomies on what drives human behaviour (e.g., Maslow, 1954; Max-Neef, 1992; Kenrick, Griskevicius, Neuberg & Schaller, 2010). For modelling needs in the HUMAT we distinguish between three main categories of needs: (1) experiential needs, which relate to e.g. comfort and costs, (2) social needs, related to e.g. social approval and status, and (3) value needs, related to e.g. autonomy, biosphere and societal goals. Firstly, this distinction introduces trade-offs for the agents concerning how behavioural options satisfy the different need categories. Next, this categorisation opens up the possibility to allow for differences in satisfaction-depletion dynamics of the different needs, which may be relative fast for experiential needs, and slower for social and value needs. Third, trade offs between different needs may result in the experience of dissonances, which will have an impact on the cognitions and actions an agent engages in.

When considering behavioural alternatives, HUMATS prefer the most satisfying option that they are aware of, based on an additive function of the expected/experienced satisfaction of the three needs. However, when this option sufficiently dissatisfies one (or more) needs, a motivational state of **cognitive dissonance** is experienced and HUMATS face a dilemma.

Three different types of dissonances can be identified based on the type of trade off between the needs. The **experiential dilemma** occurs when a behaviour yields satisfaction on social needs and values and dissatisfaction on experiential needs, or when the experiential needs are satisfied and social needs and values are dissatisfied. For example, when an agent is considering insulating its house. Insulation would be costly and disrupt the agent's life (dissatisfaction on experiential needs), but everybody else is involved in renovating (satisfaction on social needs) and the environmental advantages are being supported (satisfaction on values).

The **social dilemma** occurs when a behaviour yields satisfaction on experiential needs and values and dissatisfaction on social needs, or when the social needs are satisfied and the experiential needs and values are dissatisfied. For example, an agent is considering biking to work. Biking is healthy, fast, and cheap (satisfaction on experiential needs) and sustainable (satisfaction on values) but it is the social exception (dissatisfaction on social needs, but for an anti-conformist this would be very satisfying!).

The **value dilemma** occurs when a behaviour yields satisfaction on experiential needs and social needs and values are dissatisfied, or when values are satisfied and experiential and social needs are dissatisfied (the die-hard principal person). For example, when an agent considers driving a car to work this is comfortable (satisfaction on experiential needs), and everyone else does it (satisfaction on social needs), but it negatively impacts the environment (dissatisfaction on values).

Typical strategies to resolve these dilemmas are behavioural change, the adjustment of beliefs, convincing others to change behaviour and adjusting one's social network (befriending/unfriending). As posited by theory (Festinger 1987, 1999), dissonance between cognitions (e.g. tension occurring when activating environmental value "I care about the environment" and a cognition "I am driving a car to work"; in HUMAT pre-defined as given types of dilemmas agents can face) is a motivational force for change in knowledge (e.g. reducing the importance of caring about the environment) or behaviour (e.g. choosing a more sustainable mode of transport from available behavioural alternatives). Harmon-Jones and Harmon-Jones (2002), in their action-based model of dissonance, hypothesise that the reason for discomfort caused by dissonant cognitions comes from the fact that inconsistent cognitions have the potential of interfering with effective action. Cognitions serve as guides for behavior, so when cognitions are in conflict, behavior will be impeded (Harmon-Jones & Harmon-Jones 2018, p. 74). Therefore, when dissonance exceeds individual tolerance threshold, it needs to be actively resolved so that behaviour can occur. Agents can be equipped with a different threshold for tolerating dissonance, which is related to the personality trait of need for closure.

3.2: Choose preferred alternative

Following the evaluation of behavioural alternatives the HUMAT agent chooses a preferred alternative. If one behavioural option is present that clearly provides the best outcomes for all three groups of needs the choice is simple.

When the behavioural options on the average provide a comparable overall need satisfaction, but differ considering the degree of need satisfaction for the three different groups, the agent is confronted with dilemmas and associated dissonances. Dissonance reduction strategies may be used to alter the relevance of the three need related outcomes. For example, when an agent likes the taste of a particular food (e.g. chicken), and at the same time is aware that producing this food violates the agents values (e.g. animal welfare), the agent may experience a dissonance. The agent can reduce the cognitive dissonance by e.g. reducing the perceived tastiness of the food (chicken isn't that tasty after all), or by reducing the belief that this is being produced in disagreement with its values (the animal suffering is neglected).

If these dissonance resolution strategies are close concerning their difficulty (threshold), and two similarly satisfying behavioural alternatives evoke a similar level of cognitive dissonance, the agents have a preference for the behaviour that is more satisfactory on the experiential need, thus following behaviourist principles of preferring a short temporal distance between behaviour and reward. Hence the HUMAT agents, when facing a very difficult choice between very similar behaviours, tend to lean towards hedonism. If after this step still no decision can be made the agents will choose randomly between the competing behavioral options.

Brehm's motivation intensity theory proposes that people manage their resources following a conservation principle (Brehm et al., 1983; Brehm & Self, 1989). Therefore effort required to execute a behaviour will only be exerted (1) to the extent that it is needed and (2) only when its expenditure is justified (return on the effort is expected). The agents in HUMAT assume that with every iteration of the agent-based model, HUMATS execute one of the behavioural alternatives that is available to them, i.e. success of a behavioural alternative is viewed as both possible and worth the investment that it will require. In such cases the amount of effort exerted by HUMATS corresponds to difficulty of the behaviour. Here difficulty of behaviour is measured by the amount of dissonance.

As stated by Brehm's theory of motivation, the higher the motivation (i.e. lower actual or predicted satisfaction from a behavioural alternative), the more effortful strategies can be implemented in the search of a better alternative. Here: the higher level of dissonance, the more effortful strategies HUMAT can implement to resolve it (citation).

Ex ante dissonance reduction strategies:

Dissonance reduction can be done in different ways. Often dissonant cognitions are being suppressed or ignored as an effective dissonance reduction strategy (citation). We first acknowledge that if people have core-cognitions or generative cognitions (see p 11), they will neither ignore dissonances related to these cognitions, nor compromise their identities, and they

will prefer dissonance resolution strategies that do not involve the adjustment of these core-cognitions. Core-cognitions are related to values. For example, a convinced vegan is not likely to accept meat for a Christmas dinner, and a car aficionado will go great lengths to persist in using the car for individual transportation.

Core-value people never compromise on their values, therefore they do not experience all types of possible dilemmas. The experiential dilemma the experience is 1a option (satisfied on social and values but unsatisfied on experiential), the social dilemma is 2a option (satisfied on experiential and values but unsatisfied on social) and the values dilemma is 3b (satisfied on values and unsatisfied on experiential and social). Therefore they only change composition of their ego-networks in social dilemma and values dilemma.

Because agents with a core value cannot reduce their dissonance by changing their value, in case of a low social satisfaction they often have to rely on trying to convert other people to their values, or change their network (befriend people who behave similarly).

If core values are not at stake, depending on the type of dilemma, different sequences of strategies to reduce this dissonance can be followed.

Ex ante-strategies to deal with cognitive dissonance, according to difficulty

1: distraction and forgetting of experiential outcomes (e.g., forgetting the cold draft of a non-isolated house when insulation is discussed in summer)

2a: changing dissonant cognitions (e.g., reducing the cognition of biking being uncomfortable - decrease the satisfaction of experiential)

2b: changing consonant cognitions (e.g., adding reading time on public transportation as a positive outcome - increase satisfaction of consonant cognitions (social and/or values))

3. For cases of dilemmas, when social values are dissatisfied - signalling to change other people's behaviour + actively looking for people to befriend, who act similarly to what you want to do (looking for people who are similarly dissatisfied) + unfriending people, who act differently or have opposite cognitions.

Because at this stage HUMAT agents have already made a decision about action, dissonance resolution strategies are employed only to confirm the decision. Therefore, the search for information (changing cognitions) is biased in favour of chosen behaviour.

Communication among HUMATs is considered as a result of a motivational state of cognitive dissonance that inspires agents either to inquire about information from a specific part of their ego-networks or to share information with specific members of the ego-network. When inquiring, HUMATs try to preserve their core cognitions and activate a search that maximises the probability of receiving information that fits their own world views (homogeneity in activating specific person in an ego network).

Ex-ante depreciation of the non-chosen behaviour

The resulting dissonance will be dealt with by changing the importance of needs or cognitions responsible for the dissonance. This implies the depreciation of the not-chosen behaviour, and the appreciation of the chosen behaviour, and relates to post-consumption dissonance reduction (e.g., Cohen, Goldberg, 1970). Depreciation of similar behavioural alternative, which was not chosen as the preferred one, goes through the same dissonance resolution strategies (but in an inverted order - the more similar the behavioural alternatives, the stronger the drive to differentiate between them and depreciate the one that was not chosen) as appreciation of the preferred alternative.

After all of the strategies, the dissonance might still not be resolved fully. HUMAT acts anyway, because an action has to be taken. But it can utilise additional resolution strategies post factum.

3.3: Act

3.4: Experience effects

Following the performance of behaviour, the HUMAT agent will experience the outcomes of behaviour. But effects of behaviour can also be experienced by being informed about the outcomes of a (new) behaviour (by agents in the ego network), or by observing other agents' outcomes (e.g. observing population behaviour).

Evaluations of outcomes can change due to (1) experiencing the outcome during behaviour (habits) and (2) observing others experiencing the outcomes, and (3) communicating about the outcomes. The magnitude of change may be largest for actual experiences, and lowest for communications.

For example, a car driving commuter who strongly values comfort may have a strong cognition (experiential) that car driving is comfortable, and a weak cognition (no experience) that the tram is a comfortable mode of transportation. When communicated that the tram is comfortable, the cognition will change a bit. A direct experience however will have a much more profound impact on the evaluation of the tram as an (un)comfortable alternative for the car. As such, one negative experience may result in a persistent and strong negative cognition.

How dilemmas and satisfaction affect information seeking, cognition and behaviour selection

High satisfaction

When an agent is highly satisfied (high S_{i,j,a,t_n}), it will not change behaviour, nor engage in any informational processing. Repetition of the behaviour currently top-of-stack is the decision strategy the HUMAT engages in.

Moderate satisfaction

When $S_{i,j,a,t}$ is lower than expected, one of the three dissonance-dilemmas may rise. First, the agent will check its memory stack for a behaviour that is perceived to provide a higher need satisfaction. If a better behaviour is found, the agent will switch behaviour. If no better behaviour is found in memory, the agent can engage in different strategies depending on the type of dilemma. Much of these strategies relate to changing cognitions or the importance of needs to increase the experienced satisfaction and reduce the dissonance. Much research on these processes has been done under the heading of post-purchase dissonance reduction (Milliman & Decker, 1990).

Subsistence dilemma - (1) try being more satisfied by activating positive cognitions and suppressing negative cognitions. For example, activate cognitions on health when it is raining and you are biking (I'm a real sportsman), and deactivate cognitions on the lack-of-comfort of your non-insulated house (it's not that bad). (2) sometimes little adjustments can be made to improve the existent behaviour, e.g. buy rain clothes and wait for showers to pass when you bike (e.g. the rainshower radar is a very popular app in NL), or buy thick curtains to increase the comfort of your house.

Social dilemma - (1) when a conformist agent is satisfied with experiential and value outcomes, but its social satisfaction is lower because others behave different, the agent can try convince others to change their behaviour. This is the key driver of active signalling to relevant ego-network agents can engage in. (2) when others are not likely to conform, the importance of the social need S_i can be decreased to increase the overall satisfaction level (become more non-conformist), and (3) the agent can decide to stop interacting with dissimilar others and interact with similars as well (restructuring of the social network). The latter process may give rise to the clustering of agents that agree on a certain topic, such as an interest group focussing on the ecological value of the Noorderplantsoen park.

Personal dilemma - (1) When your experiential and social needs are satisfied, but your behaviour does not really satisfy your values, the agent can deactivate cognitions that are negative, and activate cognitions that are positive. For example, a car driving agent - when all others are also driving by car, may deactivate cognitions related to environmental damage, and activate cognitions on deserving a comfortable life. (2) It is also possible to reduce the importance of the values ($V_{i,j,t}$) to increase the average overall satisfaction. Note that if values are generative, other cognitions will be changed (either the satisfaction level or the importance) to match the non-negotiable aspects of HUMATs identity.

Low satisfaction

When the $S_{i,j,a,t}$ is even lower, the agent will actively engage in searching behaviour to (1) update values of the existing behavioural options in the memory by asking agents in the network that perform these behaviours after their values, and/or (2) scan for new behaviours - inquiry strategy in the ego-network.

Social dilemma - convince others to change...

Extreme low satisfaction

When all three needs are very low, hardly any dissonance will be experienced. All effort thus will be focussed on finding alternative behaviours that improve the satisfaction (on at least one of the needs). The agent will actively explore for alternatives and update the memory stack (optimising)

HUMAT resolves residual cognitive dissonance (ex-post)

Maybe you choose the path of either (1) going back to your old self or (2) becoming a new self depending on how satisfying the new behaviour turns out to be. What would be the relationship between the expected level of satisfaction and the actual level of satisfaction.

Post factum dissonance reduction strategies:

1. Denial of responsibility (after doing something against your cognitions) - easy
 - a. Especially if availability was an issue - not sure if this is to be modelled - "I could not do anything better"
2. Trivialisation and self-affirmation (Self-affirmation, which occurs when participants' important values are made salient, is a dissonance reduction strategy originally tested by Steele and Liu) - moderately difficult
 - a. agency is HUMAT's
 - b. Strategy that makes it possible for groups of cognitions to regain its original importance? (from before the action)
3. Adding consonant cognitions: inquiring about information within ego-network - moderate
4. Adding consonant cognitions: inquiring outside ego-network - moderate to hard
5. Compensatory behaviour (after doing something that was against your cognitions)
6. Signalling to your ego-network
7. Changing the composition of your ego network: adding new friends
8. Changing the compositions of your ego network: unfriending
9. Rebellion

After the behaviour - what happens to changed cognitions? Implementing the concept of resilience of cognitions? Increase/decrease in importance is temporary and after the cognitions return to their original importances. Only if the behaviour is repeated enough times, the cognitions are less flexible to come back to its original importance and the importance permanently changes to be more aligned with habits.

Experiences of recurring dissonance - a dissonance resolution strategy might become habitual.

Activating needs when observing other HUMATS behaviour. Relevant for observable behaviours.

3.5: Update memory

HUMATS are equipped with cognitive representations of past evaluations of possible behavioural alternatives. At any given point in time HUMAT chooses the most satisfying behaviour from possible behavioural alternatives. **Memory** of a HUMAT is a stack of behavioural alternatives ranked according to their multiple need satisfying capacity, as is graphically depicted in Figure 4. Different behavioural alternatives are described with different weights and balloons expressing the experienced and perceived advantages and disadvantages of behaviours (i.e. cognitions relating to these evaluations). The behaviour on top of the stack is performed and provides the level of need satisfaction experienced by the agent ($S_{i,j}^{p,t_n}$ in eq. 1, p. 5). The more positive outcomes and the fewer negative ones, the higher the need satisfying capacity of a behaviour. From the perspective of social innovation it is important to include the introduction of plans as potential new behaviours. Hence a HUMAT should be capable of evaluating an imaginative situation, e.g. having a decent biking infrastructure in a town that currently is car-oriented. Addressing the cross-regional dimension of SIT, HUMATS can have experiences from a different city/community. If this results in a perception that a particular behaviour will result in the most favourable outcomes, provided certain policies at place (e.g. infrastructure), the HUMATS could share this as a plan, and when a sufficient number of HUMATS would have this new behaviour on top GIVEN supporting policy (e.g. infrastructure) a co-creative process with community and policy-makers could start.

Figure 4: the memory stack of behavioural outcomes.

Empirical note

The memory stack can have different sizes, depending on the number of possible behavioural alternatives a person is perceiving. Identification of possible behavioural alternatives and associated cognitions can take place during Focus Group Interviews. **Simple stacks** address e.g. **binary one-way tipping choices**, such as isolating your house. Once isolated, the choice of de-isolating is virtually a non-option. More **complex stacks** can be created with the support of machine learning analyses of survey data. **Decision trees** can provide information on conditional rules that describe under what condition which behavioural alternative is preferable. The decision trees are emergent properties resulting from performing behaviour multiple times in different conditions and describe if-then rules for critical outcomes (the important weights).

Figure 4 shows that lower stacked behaviours display fewer (dis)advantages. This expresses that agents have fewer cognitions (knowledge) on less familiar/new behaviours. Information on (dis)advantages can increase due to observation of new behaviours, and receiving new information. For example, the cognitions (knowledge) on the (dis)advantages of insulating a house will expand after receiving information from an energy company about the savings, and

stories on the costs, efforts and benefits from a friend that insulated her house. The more information an agent has on the (dis)advantages of different behaviours, the more **experiences** the agent has. This does not mean the agent is an **expert**, as the information may be biased and incorrect. Importantly, having executed a particular behaviour may result in more cognitions than being informed by other people or observing. For example, experiencing sour buttocks as a newbie cyclists is something people are more likely to experience than to observe or explicitly be told about by more experienced cyclists that do not have this experience (anymore).

The individual ranking of behavioural alternatives is dynamic. The memory and hence the ordering of the memory stack is dynamically changing depending on (1) the **actually experienced satisfaction** (e.g. new tarmac makes biking more comfortable), (2) a different weighting of outcomes (e.g. wind & rain make a lack of comfort as **outcome more salient**), (3) adding **new outcomes** (e.g., discovering a new shorter cycling route), (4) the current **need at focus**, (e.g. values are being discussed; observing other HUMATs has a capacity of activating groups of values), etc.. Different processes thus impact the composition of the outcomes and the order of the behavioural stack. Relevant theories on salience of outcomes and needs are for example *A Focus Theory of Normative Conduct* (Cialdini, Kallgren and Reno, 1990) and *Goal Frame Theory* (Lindenberg & Steg, 2007).

Changes in need satisfaction and trade-offs between different outcomes result in the experience of dissatisfaction and dissonances, that drive the agent to consider alternative behaviour or changing beliefs.

3: Discussion on possible applications referring to SMARTEES cases

ODD protocol?
First code available?

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Website: <http://local-social-innovation.eu>

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Fragments

Birds of a feather flock... different feathers can be seen in humans as well. Many flock on the basis of daily consumptive and visible behaviours. Experiential similarity is one. Others flock with popular others, trying to build up social reputation by balancing between conformity and following - or being -v the deviant. This is social similarity. And finally, values help people to collaborate on keeping society as it is, or changing it. These three similarities play different roles depending on the dominant needs associated with a decision. The Noorderplantsoen case relates to experiences concerning use before and after the colour, social is to be investigated, and values relate to visions of the city (environment, amusement, accessibility).

Whereas birds of a feather flock, humans form bonds on different dimensions that can be related to the different needs. And as a consequence we have different groups of people we connect with on different occasions: family, colleagues, people you meet in free-time activities such as a choir or a sports club, and political & neighborhood organisations.

Experiential network can be large in visible behaviour, you observe proportions of behaviour in your community (e.g. traffic can be observed).

Social network is smaller - similarity & attraction. Dimensions of similarity. Check EROS paper.

Value network is with more intimate others - small.

1: Transitions in communities, how sustainable practices spread

- The cases that are relevant, and differences in social dynamics (habits versus investments, public visible versus private)
- The theories that are relevant in understanding human behaviour (Jager Ernst)
- The problems of implementing theory in ABM
- ABM providing a platform for integrating theories: dynamical theories

2: The HUMAT as an integrative modelling framework

- Basic ideas, existing integrative models, the lacking of (1) outgoing communication, (2) dissonance, (3) meaningful networks
- Explanation of the architecture - SMARTTEES deliverable + section on networks

Human needs: we are not an unity: three main systems with different foci: modelling direct (anticipated) experiences, group belongingness and (deep) values.

Visibility of experiential outcomes: this is the most you see of the crowd: proxy of happiness

Section on networks: we are a species

Birds of a feather flock... different feathers can be seen in humans as well. Many flock on the basis of daily consumptive and visible behaviours. Experiential similarity the is. Others flock with popular others, trying to built up social reputation by balancing between conformity and following - or being -v the deviant. This is social similarity. And finally, values help people to collaborate on keeping society as it is, or changing it. These three similarities play different roles depending on the dominant needs associated with a decision. The Noorderplantsoen case relates to experiences concerning use before and after the colure, , social is to be investigated, and values relate to visions of the city (environment, amusement, accessibility).

Whereas birds of a feather flock, humans form bonds on different dimensions that can be related to the different needs. And as a consequence we have different groups of people we connect with on different occasions: family, colleagues, people you meet in free-time activities such as a choir or a sports club, and political & neighborhood organisations.

Experiential network can be large in visible behaviour, you observe proportions of behaviour in your community (e.g. traffic can be observed).

Social network is smaller - similarity & attraction. Dimensions of similarity. Check EROS paper.

Value network is with more intimate others - small.

The perfect choice does not exist: How different needs affect our decision making and dissonance reduction.

Consumat + outward communication to reduce dissonance.

ODD?

Needs

Formulated, the overall **expected (p) (dis)satisfaction from a behavioural alternative i for HUMAT j at time tn** ($S_{ij}^{p,tn}$, $<-1;1>$) is an additive function of the extent of a need satisfaction that the behavioral alternative provides multiplied by the importance of a respective group of needs:

$$S_{ij}^{p,tn} = \frac{I_{e,j}^{tn} S_{i,e,j}^{p,tn} + I_{s,j}^{tn} S_{i,s,j}^{p,tn} + I_{v,j}^{tn} S_{i,v,j}^{p,tn}}{3}, \quad (\text{eq. 1})$$

where:

$I_{e,j}^{tn}$ - importance of experiential need for HUMAT j (*theoretical values* $<0;1>$); *initiation: trunc sigmoid distribution*) - importance of a group of needs is a personality trait and is not influenced by a particular behavioural alternative,

$S_{i,e,j}^{p,tn}$ - expected satisfaction from behavioural alternative i on experiential need for HUMAT j at time tn (*theoretical values* $<-1;1>$; *initiation: left-skewed distribution assuming that most people as satisfied with their habit*),

$I_{s,j}^{tn}$ - importance of social need for HUMAT j (*theoretical values* $<0;1>$); *initiation: trunc normal distribution*),

$S_{i,s,j}^{p,tn}$ - expected satisfaction from behavioural alternative i on social need for HUMAT j at time tn (*theoretical values* $<-1;1>$; *for conformists - % of similar behaviour in ego-network, centered at 0 for individual preference on conformism; initiation: left-skewed*),

$I_{v,j}^{tn}$ - importance of values for HUMAT j (*theoretical values* $<0;1>$); *initiation: trunc normal distribution*),

$S_{i,v,j}^{p,t_n}$ - expected satisfaction from behavioural alternative i on values for HUMAT j at time t_n (theoretical values $\langle -1;1 \rangle$; initiation: left-skewed).

Dissonance

Dissonances occur when a behaviour satisfies one group of needs, but at the same time brings dissatisfaction on another group of needs (e.g. driving a car satisfies HUMAT's experiential need because a car is comfortable, but brings dissatisfaction on values because it pollutes the environment). Behavioural alternative i with respect to k -th group of needs for HUMAT j ,

$$E_{i,k,j}^{t_n} = I_{k,j}^{t_n} S_{i,k,j}^{p,t_n}; k \in \{e,s,v\}, \quad (\text{eq. 2})$$

can be:

- Dissatisfying (i.e. $I_{k,j}^{t_n} S_{i,k,j}^{p,t_n} \in \langle -1;0 \rangle$),
- Neutral (i.e. $I_{k,j}^{t_n} S_{i,k,j}^{p,t_n} = 0$),
- Satisfying (i.e. $I_{k,j}^{t_n} S_{i,k,j}^{p,t_n} \in (0;1 \rangle$).

A two dimensional table mapping out possible dissonances between an experiential need (e) and values (v) with respect to behavioural alternative i for HUMAT j is presented in Table 2:

		$E_{i,e,j}^{t_n}$		
		$\langle -1;0 \rangle$	0	$(0;1 \rangle$
$E_{i,v,j}^{t_n}$	$\langle -1;0 \rangle$	+	+	-
	0	+	+	+
	$(0;1 \rangle$	-	+	+

Table 2. Possible dissonances between two groups of needs.

+ represents consonance between groups of needs;
 - represents dissonance between groups of needs.

If behaviour i denotes driving a car, the dissonance between highly satisfied experiential need and low satisfaction on values is visible in column 5 row 3 of the table. If behaviour i denotes riding a bike in London, the dissonance between high satisfaction on values and low satisfaction on experiential need is visible in column 3, row 5.

Amount of dissonance that a behavioural alternative i evokes in HUMAT j at time t_n ($D_{i,j}^{t_n}$) is calculated as follows:

$$D_{i,j}^{t_n} = \frac{2d}{d+c}, \quad (\text{eq. 3})$$

where:

d - dissonant cognitions, i.e. $\min(\sum \text{satisfying } E_{i,k,j}, \sum \text{dissatisfying } E_{i,k,j})$,

c - consonant cognitions, i.e. $\max(\sum \text{satisfying } E_{i,k,j}, \sum \text{dissatisfying } E_{i,k,j})$.